

Royal Conservatoire of Scotland

MA Psychology in the Arts

Negotiated Research Project

*An autoethnographic exploration of music-assisted progressive muscle
relaxation*

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Abstract

The following study will serve as an autoethnographic exploration of my personal experience engaging in a music-assisted progressive muscle relaxation protocol over a period of 9 days. Progressive muscle relaxation (PMR) was a protocol initially designed by American physician E. Jacobson (Edmund, 1929) as a method of deep muscle relaxation which seeks to help reduce stress and anxiety. Around the same time Jacobson's development of PMR was published, post World War 1, so to was music therapy gaining popularity (Montinari *et al.*, 2018). The first applications of music-assisted PMR were thought to have arisen around this time, combining the benefits of both the protocol and music itself as an effective aid to help reduce stress and anxiety. The exercise does this by orderly tensing and then relaxing muscle groups throughout the body to combat muscle tension developed alongside stressful situations or thoughts (Edmund, 1929).

Across the body of research examined in the following literature review, the musical stimuli that accompanied each protocol was preselected the vast majority of the time. This research stems out of a desire to test not only curated music, but my selection of music as well, in order to explore which stimuli category I respond the most favourably to, build an in-depth knowledge of the topic and reflect over my own experience with the protocol through thematic analysis and comparison of biofeedback data to my qualitative experience

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Introduction

Progressive Muscle Relaxation is an exercise that aims to help reduce stress and anxiety by slowly tensing and then relaxing muscles in the body (ABU Health Board, 2014) and has shown to be effective as a therapeutic intervention when combined with musical stimuli (Kim, 2008). This research aims to explore how music influences my personal experience engaging with a PMR protocol over 9 days.

To address the research aim, the following objectives will be met.

- The 9-day project will be split into 3 stimuli conditions.
 - Days 1 to 3, no music
 - Days 4 to 6, my choice of music
 - Day 7 to 9, non-choice curated music
- During the sessions, biofeedback data will be collected, and I will journal my experiences afterwards.
- Data will be analysed through thematic analysis and descriptive statistics.

This will be carried out in order to be able to reflect upon the choices to see what impact each condition has on the PMR protocol and to build an in-depth knowledge of PMR by engaging with both structured and non-structured journaling. By the end of this research, the aim is to be able to identify what influence music had on the PMR protocol for myself and develop my knowledge of the area of inquiry by reflecting over my experience with the protocol through thematic analysis and comparison of biofeedback data to my qualitative experience.

Before the data is gathered and analysed, it is first important to provide a detailed look at what PMR is, what its uses are and how it functions, as well as establish the research context that surrounds the topic area.

Progressive Muscle Relaxation

In 1929, it was the general opinion of the research community that there was perhaps no greater general remedy than rest (Edmund, 1929). This holds true today with modern studies showing the positive impact adequate rest and relaxation has upon our mental and physical wellbeing, productivity, cognitive function and mental health (Asp, 2015; Lamp *et al.*, 2019). While it is certainly not a definitive answer to each and every issue that may arise over a given individual's life, it is an important factor in general health. At the time that Edmund Jacobson was developing the PMR protocol, there was only scattered and occasional use of structured relaxation in the practice of medicine. This was a time in which doctors would prescribe tepid baths, warm drinks, massages and drug sedatives to promote sleep and relaxation (Edmund, 1929). It was the lack of systematic and consistent relaxation techniques available at the time that served as the basis for the development of Progressive Muscle Relaxation.

PMR was originally developed based on the theory that the psychobiological state ¹of neuromuscular hypertension ²can be the basis for a variety of emotional states and psychosomatic diseases (Edmund, 1929). By orderly contracting and then relaxing muscle groups throughout the body and, in particular, focusing on the sensation of

¹ The interaction of psychological and biological factors

² Increased muscle tone and tension beyond what is needed for regular function

tension and release, PMR addresses our psychobiological state by helping to alleviate muscle tension developed as a common manifestation of stress and anxiety (Pluess, Conrad and Wilhelm, 2009). The interaction of both physical and emotional relaxation can help to address multiple issues related to psychological stress and anxiety (Conrad and Roth, 2007). As hypertension can be both localised as well as throughout the body, the PMR protocol can help to address both by following each step through to completion. Even in its infancy, the PMR protocol had many forms depending on the condition it was being used to help address. In clinical settings, it was initially used as a supplementary aid and deployed in lower number of total sessions, the length of which was shortened, than say persistent issues such as anxiety and depression, in which longer and more frequent sessions enabled more effective assistance in dealing with various issues. One of the more prevalent factors in the efficacy of the protocol is securing the co-operation of the participant and identifying the participant's aptitude in engaging with PMR. Those who have never thought about the difference between tension and nervous excitement or relaxation and nervous calm may be initially sceptical. Jacobson comments on this saying,

“If he will co-operate, it is well to let his scepticism remain, for it will gradually yield when his observations and insight progress.”

It is important to note here that my personal engagement with the protocol comes from a position of knowledge. While I am not attempting to evaluate the efficacy of the protocol as a whole, the way in which I react to it may be enhanced via my knowledge, the reasons why I am engaging with the protocol/self-co-operation and practice of PMR.

Muscle relaxation is not simply a protocol in which you tense and relax muscle groups. It aims to teach the participant how to recognise and control muscular contraction as well. When done for the first time, if the individual is requested to relax, they may find difficulty as they are unaware of where their tension lies in the body. This issue was addressed by Jacobson when he developed the idea of cultivating the individual's muscle-sense. By focusing initially on only one larger muscle group in isolation, while maintaining awareness of other sensations, such as the feeling of clothes, the bed or chair you are sitting on etc. the individual gains the ability to discriminate between the muscle contraction and external stimuli as well as how the muscles that aren't contracted feel in order to understand and identify tension or lack thereof. Jacobson found that this practice greatly aided in the efficacy of the protocol when carried out pre-emptively, and regarding the following research, I have personally developed a sense of muscle and tension awareness beforehand, utilising this method.

The PMR protocol has been adapted multiple times since its initial development and presentation at Harvard University in 1908. Bernstein and Borkovec (1976), Wolpe (1980), and Pelletier (2004) have all provided functional updates to meet the needs of a wider range of use cases than the protocol was initially designed to address. As such, the utility provided by the protocol has been evidenced in various fields and addresses a wide range of both clinical conditions and mental disorders. On the clinical side, it has been found beneficial in alleviating negative symptoms of pain syndromes (Gay, Philippot and Luminet, 2002), headaches (Schlutter, Golden and Blume, 1980), asthma (Grover, Kumaraiah and Prasadrao, 2002), and tinnitus (Storb and Strahl, 2006). Regarding mental conditions, it provides similar value in helping to manage adverse symptoms in anxiety and stress disorders (Conrad and Roth, 2007), schizophrenia (Vancampfort *et al.*, 2013),

insomnia (Wang *et al.*, 2016; Xiao *et al.*, 2020; Ruano *et al.*, 2022) and depression (Muhammad Khir *et al.*, 2024).

Music-Assisted PMR

While the concept of music as a method for healing, resting and relaxing has been around for thousands of years (Meymandi, 2009). The profession of music therapy was only formed in the mid-20th century (AMTA, 2016). Veterans hospitals after the 1st and 2nd World Wars noticed the positive effects that music had on patients' mental and physical well-being and started hiring musicians to perform at hospitals (Yinger, 2018). These musicians needed to be trained to appropriately deal with hospital patients, and so in America, this was how the development of music therapy programmes began. It wasn't until the 1990s, however, that the first cases of music therapy and PMR being used in conjunction with one another were documented by two master's degree students at the University of West Michigan, Clarkson (1991) and Gladfelter (1992). However, these studies had limited insight into the effects of the musical stimuli due to their research design and limitations.

Music therapy interventions are often split into a few different categories, such as.

- Listening to music (music-assisted relaxation, music and imagery)
- Talking about music (music discussion, lyric analysis)
- Making music (improvising, playing instruments, singing, composing)
- Moving to music (dancing, exercise)

(Yinger, 2018)

In the context of PMR, it is the first category of listening to music that is used as the intervention. Music listening has been found to have a wide range of benefits. Parasympathetic activation³ has been found to be amplified when listening to theta-wave binaural beats⁴ (McConnell *et al.*, 2014). By playing music that synchronises with the breath of the participant, music can help to anchor focus and reduce intrusive thought, which in the context of PMR implies that it can be used as an external attentional scaffold during somatic practice (Leslie *et al.*, 2019). It has also been effective in helping with emotional regulation (Moore, 2013) which, when practicing PMR over longer periods of time, may yield compounding positive results. It is for reasons such as these that the efficacy of the protocol may be enhanced with the addition of musical stimuli.

In the case of the musical stimuli itself, there are three categories the music may fall into regarding how the stimuli were selected and their role. Self-selected music is music chosen exclusively by the participant to be played throughout the course of the session. Practitioner-selected music, where the music therapist or PMR specialist curates the music for the individual to listen to, or participant selection from a practitioner-curated selection, where the individual selects from a choice of provided music. Throughout the research context section, current research will be evaluated to show which categories are most often selected and why this research was developed, but to summarise, there is little current research that shows the differences between these categories.

³ Part of the autonomic nervous system responsible for slowing heart rate, breath and blood pressure upon activation

⁴ Theta-wave binaural beats are a type of auditory illusion created by playing two different sound frequencies, one in each ear, that result in the perception of a third, lower frequency tone within the theta range (4-7 or 4-8 Hz)

Research Context

Having established what Progressive Muscle Relaxation is, the following will seek to provide the context for why it was chosen as the vessel for which to conduct this research. Across the body of research done into the efficacy of PMR, there are few systematic reviews into its benefits when combined with music as a therapeutic intervention. Muhammad Khir *et al.* (2024) provide a detailed look at existing literature in their meta-analysis and review of 46 publications, spanning 16 countries and 3402 adults, to evaluate PMR as an intervention. Out of these 46 publications, a total of 4 included music to accompany the protocol. The total number of studies retrieved before the initial screening phase was 3205, with 1336 removed as they were duplicate papers. Following this, 65 were not retrieved due to access restrictions, and the remainder did not meet their specified criteria for the systematic review. It is important to note that their criteria for inclusion were split into two categories, namely;

- Publications that explore the effects of PMR on stress, anxiety and depression in adults, either in isolation or in combination with additional intervention approaches, such as incorporating music into the protocol
- Publications that implemented a rigorous methodology utilising Randomised Controlled Trial (RCT) or Quasi-Experimental Design (QED).

Out of the 4 studies included that fit the criteria and included music, none of them detail giving the participants a direct choice of musical stimuli. Through analysis of these larger scale RCT and QED style studies (Robb, 2000; K *et al.*, 2018; Ozgundondu and Gok Metin, 2019; Gallego-Gómez *et al.*, 2020) it can be observed that K *et al.* (2018) did not specify

which music was utilized and the other 3 studies utilized curated music, chosen based on musicological variables, the ability to control the stimuli variable between testing groups or simply claims that the music was composed specifically to relieve tension and increase relaxation. Because of the nature of these studies, as well as the number of participants, it would not be viable to provide each participant with their own choice of music. Despite this, it is acknowledged that research supports the use of participant-preferred music (Thaut and Davis, 1993).

Shifting the focus then to more qualitative studies, as well as those not included in Muhammad Khar's (2024) analysis, that may have the flexibility to provide a participant group the ability to be more involved in the selection process, it is observed that there has been no qualitative meta-analysis of music-assisted PMR, its efficacy, music choice or analysis of musical stimuli. Individual analysis of the research done into music-assisted PMR and providing the participants with a choice in the stimuli shows a profound gap regarding an aspect that may provide value to the individual engaging in the PMR protocol. Nilsson's (2008) systematic review, as well as the meta-analysis conducted by Vetter *et al.* (2015), both suggest that participant-selected musical stimuli can yield stronger health benefits than researcher-curated music in clinical environments when utilising music in a setting designed to improve health and wellbeing, which aligns with the findings of Thaut and Davis (1993). The research done that provides the participants with a level of choice, such as Nguyen *et al.*, (2023) Singh *et al.*, (2009) and Peyee, Wing and Hwa, (2021), again offers participants a selection of music to choose from rather than their own music. This is often chosen based on principles developed by Gaston (1951) and Hanser (1985), which suggest that in order for participants to achieve optimum relaxation, the musical stimuli must fall into rigid musicological elements, such

as slow tempo, minimal instrumentation or lack of percussion and sustained legato melodic lines. Furthermore, Pelletier's (2004) meta-analysis on stress reduction and musical stimuli develops these ideas by concluding that these musicological elements are effective in stress reduction and relaxation.

Each previously mentioned meta-analysis, study or trial sought to evaluate the effects of PMR, musical stimuli, or both, from a positivist⁵ positionality. This research stems from the desire to instead provide a pragmatic research framework that incorporates both interpretivist⁶ viewpoints and positivist data gathering methods, which has not yet been undertaken regarding the area of inquiry.

One of the few noted studies that provided the participants with a free choice of music stimuli was Kim's (2008) research into the effects of music therapy on helping musicians manage music performance anxiety (MPA). In which the principal researcher observed that there may be new directions in which music-assisted PMR can be taken regarding health and wellness. Kim (2008) acknowledges that more research is needed to provide a stronger intent to recommend PMR interventions over pharmacological interventions. However, in the context of this research, the study showed that the PMR and participant-chosen music therapy intervention combined was effective.

After examining the literature and finding a lack of interpretivist research, combined with the strong knowledge base that has been developed to show how providing participants with control over the music intervention yields effective results, as well as acknowledging

⁵ Positivism is a philosophical approach that emphasizes empirical evidence and scientific methods as the primary means of acquiring knowledge

⁶ In social science, interpretivism (or antipositivism) is a theoretical stance which proposes that the social realm cannot be studied with the methods of investigation utilized within the natural sciences, and that investigation of the social realm requires a different epistemology.

that curated music shows positive effects, this essay seeks to develop a stronger understanding of these factors from an autoethnographic standpoint.

Autoethnographic Approach

Having touched on the theoretical framework, this section will be dedicated to expanding on why an autoethnographic approach was taken. It was with the belief that from the information gathered throughout the research context that a qualitative approach was necessary to examine reactions towards musical stimuli. However, I still had the desire to measure biometrics to provide a more nuanced discussion on the effects of the stimuli, making my research design mixed methods. Initially, this design was intended for use with external participants as opposed to an autoethnographic approach. This, however, did not end up succeeding due to difficulties with application for ethical approval, and as such, I had to reconsider the aims. By evaluation of my own experiences and having now read and understood the depth of data that you can gather from yourself, I was enticed to try and engage with the protocol myself. To deeply familiarise myself with the area of inquiry, it is my lived experience that understanding is developed through personal experience. Lived inquiry was one of the prime driving factors behind developing knowledge in this area and is based on the concept of multiple ways of knowing, which recognises that knowledge is not gained through just one channel. These ideas were founded based on principles established by Bolt and Barrett (2019) in their book *Practice as Research*, and Ellis, Adams and Bochner's (2010) overview of autoethnography. As well as development of knowledge an autoethnographic approach enables me to more closely reflect on the stimuli from a personal perspective which may help to understand the choices of others before expanding the research to include external participants.

As established in the research context, there is a lack of research done regarding the effect of participant chosen music and the relationship between said stimuli and the participants' experience. In order to develop further research to help fill this gap, it is imperative for me as a researcher to understand this relationship and the effects of the stimuli to breed empathy and firsthand knowledge to more effectively design a study that is broader in scope. In order to address my amended research aims and for these reasons, autoethnography was selected.

Methodology and Procedure

Research Design

This study will implement a mixed-method design based on the theoretical framework of pragmatism as a research paradigm underpinned by the theories and approaches collated by Kaushik and Walsh (2019). Pragmatism was implemented as a paradigm suited to flexibility in the comparison and analysis of biometric data and qualitative journal entries. As well as this, it suits the needs of the research aims in helping to develop a deeper understanding of multiple data sets, the area of inquiry in general, and to help make an informed decision as to how each stimuli category affected my engagement with the PMR protocol.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval of research was granted through the Royal Conservatoire of Scotland at programme level. As this study is autoethnographic and does not engage with anything potentially mentally, physically or otherwise in nature, there is minimal risk to myself.

While there can be potential harm in autoethnography related to individual narrative and personal investments in research, this study focuses more on the scientific method of testing musical stimuli rather than uncovering and developing ideas surrounding my personality.

Standard ethical considerations, such as safe storage of data in accordance with the 2018 Data Protection Act, will be adhered to. Regarding confidentiality and anonymity, I will refer to myself throughout the body of the essay, as the research is being carried out on my lived experience. For the second stimuli group, curated music, the curator will be referred to as my supervisor at the Royal Conservatoire of Scotland.

Conflict of Interest

My positionality as the principal researcher conducting a study into my own lived experiences, as well as handling and analysis of my own data, must be acknowledged. Bias has the chance to affect all research in particular autoethnography. This will be addressed by critical reflexivity in an attempt to limit any potential personal bias that may arise. Critical reflexivity refers to the researcher being aware of their effect on the process and outcomes of research (Poerwandari, 2021). Referred to also as self-consciousness, which helps to ensure the so-called “objectivity” of the auto-ethnographer (Nazaruk, 2011). Ongoing reflexivity, as well as a structured research design and rigorous data analysis, will all be incorporated to help limit bias.

Protocol Structure and Music Conditions

Pre-Session

The research was conducted over 9 days from the 9th to the 17th of June 2025. The first stage was conducting the PMR protocol each evening at approximately 11 PM. The PMR protocol was prerecorded, 15 minutes 14 seconds in length and freely accessed via the Houston Centre for Valued Living (Appendix I). Based on the principles developed by Edmund Jacobson, this version of the protocol was condensed and designed for those who had previously engaged in the protocol or had previously cultivated a connection to their muscle-sense, the latter of which I had. Jacobson outlines the full protocol in progressive relaxation; this abbreviated version follows a similar structure, which goes through the following order of muscle contraction and then release, with each group being repeated twice.

- Right hand - *forearm, elbow*
- Left hand - *forearm, elbow*
- Face - *eyebrows, eyes, nose, jaw, forehead, mouth*
- Neck – *front and back*
- Abdomen – *shoulders, pectoral muscle, abdominis muscle*
- Right Leg – *foot, calves, thighs*
- Left Leg – *foot, calves, thighs*

The protocol was conducted in my personal office, sitting down with the lights off, and audio was played through Eris 4.5 studio monitors. Pulse rate range and distribution were measured through a Lepu Medical Technology certified Viatom FS20F pulse oximeter.

Data was relayed via Bluetooth 4.0 to the Vihealth app. The pulse oximeter was placed on my index finger before starting the session, and data was recorded from when the protocol began through to its conclusion.

Session Conditions

The trial was split into three stimuli categories, each of which lasted three sessions.

- Condition One – No musical stimuli
- Condition Two – Personal Music Curation
- Condition Three – Supervisor Curated Music

Condition one was chosen not to include musical stimuli to serve as a baseline and gauge how I reacted to the protocol in isolation. As well as this, from the positionality of a professional musician, music is often an active experience in my life. When listening to new music, I have the tendency to analyse first and then listen and appreciate second, and with music I am already familiar with, I like to try and discover new things I haven't picked up on in previous listening sessions. I am often drawn to musicological complexity or sonically varied genres and musicians, as when I listen to music, I like to be musically and emotionally engaged to derive pleasure from the experience. By excluding musical stimuli from condition one, I am focused on developing my efficacy with the PMR protocol as well as experiencing it in its original form.

Condition two adds the first musical stimuli category, comprised of three tracks chosen by myself. The selection process was straightforward in that the criteria I set were merely pieces that I was familiar with and I thought would be enjoyable to relax alongside. There was no musicological criteria; the pieces include a mix of vocals, percussion, digital

instrumentation, complex harmonies and faster tempos, all of which do not align with standard practice in choosing musical stimuli for optimum relaxation (Gaston, 1951; Hanser, 1985). It was purely personal preference at the time. The three selected tracks also had to add up to a total of roughly 15 minutes to align with the length of the protocol.

The tracks chosen were as follows:

- Sail To The Moon – *Radiohead*
- For Johann – *Ryuichi Sakamoto*
- Dawn Chorus – *Thom Yorke*

(15:33 run time)

Condition three adds the second set of musical stimuli curated by my personal supervisor. Once again, these tracks had no musicological criteria. The only framework provided regarding the curation was that it had to be relaxing in the opinion of my supervisor, and as with condition two, this ended up including different genres, instrumentation, vocals and tempos. The tracks chosen were as follows:

- Seven Days of Falling – *Esbjorn Svensson Trio*
- Ave Maria – *The Robert Shaw Choral (Schubert/Bach-Gounod)*
- Nisi Dominus R.608:4 – *Andreas Scholl (Vivaldi)*

(15:05 run time)

Post-Session

After each session was completed, the first thing that was done was sending all biometric data via email to myself, followed by naming and categorising the data on my phone in order to have two secure copies. After this was completed, I filled out a structured journal

template designed to engage reflexive thinking and evaluate my experiences methodically (see Appendix II). The entries started with evaluation of setting, environment, time of day and which condition was utilised. It then moved into questions regarding physical sensations pre- and post-session, emotional and psychological state pre- and post-session, the impact of music (and silence for condition one), sense of connection to body, breath and emotions and finally overall impact. Following this, I provided unstructured, narrative-driven commentary and thoughts regarding each individual session to further flesh out the depth of data on which to reflect and analyse.

As the sessions were conducted in the evening, my routine remained constant throughout the nine days. I would relax for roughly an hour post-session and then go to sleep. It is important to note that the days in which I had outside work engagements that ran late, the protocol was conducted an hour after returning home, showering and resting at approximately the same time each evening.

Methods of Data Analysis

By utilising a mixed methods research design, I aim to synthesise biometric data and subjective experience, which will enhance the depth of data I am able to draw from each session, leading in turn to a richer and more reflexive discussion addressing the research aims. All data generated through journal responses will be analysed using reflexive thematic analysis based on the principles described and developed by Braun and Clarke (2006). Each journal entry was combined and manually transcribed into a master document for coding and familiarisation in Microsoft Word. Coding the data into sets

then allows for the identification of key themes which were refined through detailed analysis of how each theme related to the aims of the study and existing literature.

All biofeedback data was analysed through descriptive statistics, which sought to summarise the key characteristics of the data sets through measuring central tendency, variability and frequency distribution. As heart rate and pulse range distribution have the potential to be an indicator of relaxation and stress (Buccelletti *et al.*, 2009; Goessl, Curtiss and Hofmann, 2017) this data set can help to provide valuable information on how my body reacts to each stimuli, which will be compared to my reflections in each journal entry.

Results

Quantitative Descriptive Statistics

All data sets deal with numerical continuous data through which the mean tendency was measured, and while no explicit standard deviation was extrapolated, it is implied through providing minimum and maximum heart rate values for each session.

To serve as a baseline for heart rate variability in the protocol testing, first, resting heart rate (RHR) was measured through temporal analysis over three days from the 16th of June to the 18th of June (See figure A).

Figure A

Data was collected directly after waking and directly before sleeping, and the mean was calculated between both the AM and PM readings per day, as well as all three days combined. While calculating RHR, there are multiple testing methods; this method was devised based on findings from Speed *et al.*, (2023). RHR was observed to sit at ≈ 73 BPM. Categorical groupings were devised for comparative analysis with days 1-3 named 'Condition One', 4-6 'Condition Two' and 7-9 'Condition Three'. Pulse rate range/min (PRR) was measured as soon as I sat down for the session until the conclusion of the

session. To maintain accuracy across the conditions, the 1st minute and final 20 seconds of data were removed from the analysis to account for the protocol starting 1 minute after sitting down and ending 20 seconds before getting up.

The analysis sought to understand the following 5 variables: PRR at start, PRR at end, session average, lowest PRR/session and highest PRR/session. These variables were analysed on a condition basis as well as per day and were chosen as variables best suited to identifying if there were downward trends in PRR, if PRR was elevated or decreased when paired with different stimuli and how PRR varies throughout muscle tension and release.

By performing a Paired T-Test, there were no statistically significant decreases in any of the values between condition groups; however, it was observed that there was a statistically significant difference between individual days of the protocol regarding the 5 measured variables. When comparing days 1 and 9, it was found in a one-tailed test that $p < 0.00049$, indicating a significant drop in heart rate (HR), which, regarding the research aims, indicates that I was more relaxed, calm and at ease with the protocol. This will be compared to my subjective experience through RTA in regard to the musical stimuli. However, it can be said that through a variety of factors such as familiarity with the protocol, consistent routine and consistent engagement with the protocol, HR decreased steadily throughout and by the end of the 9 days aligned more with RHR, even sometimes dropping below RHR. When asking the question then of was this decrease in heart rate due to the PMR protocol, it can confidently be confirmed that yes, the protocol was effective in decreasing heart rate.

Condition One

When visualised, condition one shows downward trends in PRR on a per-day basis (see Figure B). There was a slight fluctuation in average session heart rate with a dip on day 2 measured at =86BPM, which returned to =90BPM the following day; however, the range distribution between lowest and highest BPM narrowed over time, suggesting reduced variability by day 3. See figure C – E for session data.

Figure B

Day 1 – Figure C

HR at Start = 97BPM, HR at End = 92BPM, Session Average = 91BPM, Lowest HR = 79BPM, Highest HR = 126BPM

Day 2 – Figure D

HR at Start = 83BPM, HR at End = 80BPM, Session Average = 86BPM, Lowest HR = 68BPM, Highest HR = 109BPM

Day 3 – Figure E

HR at Start = 82BPM, HR at End = 80BPM, Session Average = 90BPM, Lowest HR = 73BPM, Highest HR = 118BPM

When viewing the heart rate data, it is observed that heart rate variability is constantly in flux throughout the sessions due to the tensing and releasing of muscle groups, which is to be expected. Accounting for the 1st minute and last 20 seconds of data not being recorded (as well as for conditions 2 and 3), the aforementioned figures show each session from condition one.

Condition Two

Condition two, being the first stimuli condition, shows far more variability throughout both the condition and on a per-session basis. HR was observed to trend downwards on days 4 and 6, but increased on day 5. As well as this average session HR was observed to be lowest on day 5 despite the upward trend in HR throughout the session. Variability was also the lowest on day 5, whereas the dispersion on day 4 in particular was largest, indicating potential overexertion during the protocol (See figure F).

Figure F

The reasons for potential overexertion, which increased variability, will be extrapolated further during reflexive thematic analysis and discussion. This extreme outlier regarding the highest measured heart rate for that session, however, can be treated as such, as the muscle group that was tensed during the spike to 180BPM was chest and abdomen, the strain on the heart naturally increased, and for the remainder of the sessions, I took note to follow Jacobson's techniques with more care. Be aware of the tension in the muscle groups first and foremost, and if no tension is identified, don't over exert the muscle group with the intention of trying to find tension that may not even be there. This proved to be the only major outlier in the highest HR for these reasons. See figure G-I for session data.

Day 4 – Figure G

HR at Start = 96BPM, HR at End = 88BPM, Session Average = 93BPM, Lowest HR = 77BPM, Highest HR = 180BPM

Day 5 – Figure H

HR at Start = 76BPM, HR at End = 82BPM, Session Average = 87BPM, Lowest HR = 70BPM, Highest HR = 114BPM

Day 6 – Figure I

HR at Start = 103BPM, HR at End = 94BPM, Session Average = 99BPM, Lowest HR = 87BPM, Highest HR = 118BPM

While day 6 shows less variability than the other days in the condition, it also shows the highest minimum heart rate throughout all conditions, sitting at ≈ 87 BPM. It was also the highest starting heart rate through each condition and the highest average HR throughout each condition.

Condition Three

Condition three was the second musical stimuli category and showed the least variability in the highest HR per session. HR generally trends downwards, with the exception of day 8 where it remained the same, however this condition recorded the lowest HR over all conditions on day 9 at 62BPM or ≈ 11 BPM under average RHR. The final day also recorded lowest session average and lowest maximum HR measured, indicating that throughout the conditions, HR variability and average trended downward overall with a consistently steady reduction in HR overall levels (See figure J).

Figure J

The final set of 3 days in condition three exhibited the strongest average decline in heart rate with an average starting HR of 86BPM trending down to 79BPM by the end of the sessions. The calculations for the percentage difference are as follows.

	Condition 1	Condition 2	Condition 3
Avg at start	87	91	86
Avg at end	84	88	79

$$\text{Percentage lower} = \frac{\text{Other Condition Avg} - \text{Condition 3 Avg}}{\text{Other Condition Avg}} \times 100$$

At Start

- Vs. Condition 1: $\frac{87-86}{87} \times 100 = 1.15\%$
- Vs. Condition 2: $\frac{91-86}{91} \times 100 = 5.49\%$

At End

- Vs. Condition 1: $\frac{84-79}{84} \times 100 = 5.95\%$
- Vs. Condition 2: $\frac{88-79}{88} \times 100 = 10.23\%$

To summarize then, it is shown that regarding the conditions as a whole, condition 3 exhibited the lowest average HR of the condition groups. HR at the end of the protocol was 5.95% lower than condition 1 and 10.23% lower than condition 2. The specific data regarding the final three days of the protocol are as follows:

Day 7 – Figure K

HR at Start = 83BPM, HR at End = 80BPM, Session Average = 86BPM, Lowest HR = 68BPM, Highest HR = 109BPM

Day 8 – Figure L

HR at Start = 83BPM, HR at End = 80BPM, Session Average = 86BPM, Lowest HR = 68BPM, Highest HR = 109BPM

Day 9 – Figure M

HR at Start = 83BPM, HR at End = 80BPM, Session Average = 86BPM, Lowest HR = 68BPM, Highest HR = 109BPM

Quantitative Results Conclusion

Having now evaluated each condition, the following observations can be made. From a descriptive perspective, heart rate was shown to decrease over time, which can be most clearly seen through average and end-of-session HR. The final day of the protocol evidences the lowest HR readings across all metrics, indicating a strong physiological relaxation effect by the end of the session, which aligns with findings shown by Ubaidillah *et al.*, (2023) on PMR and heart rate decrease over time to help reduce anxiety and stress. By briefly examining the range, there is a clear overall downward trend that remains consistent, especially regarding the lowest measured heart rate, which has a value of $87 - 62 = 25\text{BPM}$, indicating consistent gradual change. The only outlier in the range that shows an inconsistent data trend is highest HR, which, on a session basis, was affected by the spike to 180BPM on day 4, however with this point excluded the maximum HR per session also decreases over time on average.

Reflexive Thematic Analysis

While the descriptive statistical analysis provides an interesting view of biometric states throughout the protocol in order to properly contextualise this data, reflexive thematic analysis of journal entries over the 9-day period provides more detail regarding the thoughts, opinions and feelings I had at the time.

9 days' worth of journal entries regarding the experience, outlined in the methodology, were coded, and from these codes, 6 primary themes were developed with the goal of addressing the research aims and providing context for the aforementioned biometric

data, a more precise understanding of the experience and the ability to formulate a rich discussion around the area of inquiry. These themes will be evaluated in the following section with the inclusion of various sub-themes throughout that arose upon analysis and will include quotes from the journal entries as well as observations linking biometric data to subjective experiences in the discussion.

The specific themes are as follows:

- Reflexive Self-awareness and Growth
- Relaxation Responses over Emotional Responses
- Passive Listening
- Aesthetic Appreciation aids protocol outcomes
- The double-edged nature of musical engagement
- Familiarity as a Gateway to Relaxation

These themes were developed from distinct recurring sentiments that emerged in both structured journal responses and non-structured reflective entries. Familiarisation with the data deepened progressively across analysis of each condition, allowing themes to evolve alongside the revelation of new nuances found when doing each set of analysis. To create a stronger reflexive narrative as well as for analytical integrity, each theme seeks to capture a key characteristic of the condition but also builds upon and reflects on each other's conditions.

Condition One

Reflexive Self Awareness and Growth

While not a direct outcome goal of PMR, it was made evident that in the context of a study certain elements regarding efficacy could be enhanced via reflexive self-awareness. Relaxation is a process and not an immediate state (Edmund, 1929). The post-session journal entries enabled a level of reflection that had a positive impact on the protocol itself. This is made evident especially on day 1, where there was a level of initial apprehension pre-session, uncertainty post-session and then following the journal entries afterwards, a recognition of efficacy and more clarity regarding how I felt.

“Now that I have had time to reflect on the session I feel more confident in my earlier assessment that the session went well overall”

This quote was taken from the free journaling section when on day one, I observed positive but uncertain effects directly after the protocol finished, but came back to add this entry an hour after the protocol was complete. Revisiting my own experiences with added clarity may suggest a growing awareness regarding the mind-body connection and my ‘true’ experience with the protocol.

This is made more evident by the contrast between the days on this condition. Natural apprehension on day 1 appears normal regarding the circumstances under which the protocol is being engaged with. Physical sensation on day one included descriptions of mild tension, slight discomfort, but otherwise a neutral state. The descriptions of physical state changed drastically on the second two days, in which I shifted from describing my tension or vague concepts of discomfort to describing far more in depth

that there was an absence of tension throughout my muscles, I was more aware of my body, and I could confidently state I was physically relaxed. Awareness of muscle groupings certainly increased throughout the trial. On day one when asked to describe physical state after the session I described that *“I feel much looser and my body feels lighter”*, in contrast to days two and three in which I described that *“The session helped to make me aware that I was holding onto tension”*, and *“I didn’t notice any tension before but after my legs and arms feel much more at ease”*.

Regarding cognitive growth, the first day exhibited a gradual slowing of thoughts followed by a delayed shift to relaxation and peace. A sub-theme developed, however for this section was the limited cognitive and emotional reflection in the answers to questions of that nature. Especially in regard to conditions 2 and 3, condition 1 shows primary growth in physical and somatic awareness. Answers given to questions such as “how connected to your body, breath and emotions did you feel?”, provide little insight into emotional shifts or changes. This question, in particular, while not designed to get a particular answer, does give insight into what I was focused on in the moment, and for condition 1, it appears that primarily physical aspects were at the forefront of my mind.

Relaxation Response over Emotional Response

This concept of physical embodied relaxation, as opposed to a combination of physical and emotional responses, makes this condition unique and could have to do with the lack of external stimuli and a more traditional approach to the protocol. When asked to describe the aspect of silence, there were a few notable distinctions between the lack of stimuli condition and the others. The silence provided an opportunity to focus on my

breath and physical state, something that in a professional context, as a trained opera singer, I am quite familiar with.

“The silence was nice as I could focus on my breath and breathing properly. It occurred to me that I haven’t done proper breath training or exercise since I was singing full time and was nice to relax into.”

There is also the sentiment that, because of previous experience engaging with structured breathing exercises that this condition acted, in a way, more akin to said exercises with the added element of muscle relaxation. The silence served as a way in which to thoroughly relax, through both the protocol and breathing, which enhanced relaxation without drawing forth a strong emotional response. This aligns with the processes of optimum or ‘true’ relaxation that Jacobson observed in testing for his publication of Progressive Muscle Relaxation. PMR reaches its optimum efficacy for only fleeting moments of time during each session. These moments were characterised by Jacobson as moments in which the relaxation of sense organs approach completeness.

“It is during such brief periods (of time) that imagery seems altogether absent. With progressive muscle relaxation, not alone imagery, but also attention, recollection, thought processes and emotion gradually diminish.” (Edmund, 1929)

Looking then to some of the other questions asked, there are two that reinforce that this condition was aligned with the observations made, that at its core PMR intends to draw from the participant a relaxation response first and foremost. These fleeting moments were most commonly observed on the 3rd day of the condition, when I had acclimatised to the routine and motions of the protocol. When asked how present I was, there was a notable shift from initially present into deep unaware peace. There was no emotional

response, just an unawareness of surroundings and a focus on the lack of tension in my muscles, combined with a freedom and ease of breath. Regarding mental clarity and distractions, the protocol served as a grounding factor that kept my thoughts flowing with ease, not focusing on any one thing in particular, which, from my positionality, is a rare phenomenon. On day two, I describe this as follows:

“Interestingly today my thoughts started becoming a little more active towards the end of the session, but it was mainly towards factors such as equipment working and hoping that nothing would go wrong. I felt quite focused on the movements of the protocol however which kept the thoughts at bay and my mind relatively clear.”

Which by day three had progressed to:

“Zero distraction during the session, (and) my mind was very empty. The thoughts that did come flowed away with ease.”

While reflexive growth and attunement to the protocol over the first condition is an important theme to examine, the fact that this condition reflected the aims and outcomes of PMR in such an authentic manner is imperative to note when examining this condition in comparison to the other two. Regarding the research aims, this condition showed great promise in its efficacy for me personally by day three, and I am sure that, given more time, it would have continued to improve as it did over the three-day period.

Condition Two

Passive Listening

Adding the first musical stimuli to the protocol brought forth how important it was for me to be able to engage with the music passively. What I mean by this is that from the perspective of an artist-researcher trained in classical performance, when music is at the forefront of my mind, it distracts and deters from my ability to engage with the protocol on as meaningful a level as when there is no stimuli. Reflexively, this condition was such a meaningful experience because of the fact that my engagement with the music was passive and calming.

As opposed to condition one, condition two showed a far more immediate relaxation response however this could also be due to exposure to condition one first. The music chosen was familiar to me, and so I was certainly not in as analytic a mindset regarding the stimuli compared to condition three. This mindset enables the music to be a background element that enhances the experience as opposed to distracting from it.

While there was a slight initial distraction, due to volume as opposed to the music, this shifted into thoughtlessness. From the second day, when asked “How did the music affect your engagement with the PMR protocol?”, I described how effective the music was at setting a mood with which the protocol can function on.

“I loved it. All three songs working in tandem and playing one after the other to set a mood or like a general vibe was so nice.”

The way in which the music was cohesive and made sense was not distracting. This was further evidenced during day one, where despite there being a slight volume issue, I noted the following:

“Even though the first track may have been distracting at times I wouldn’t change it if it affected how relaxed and ready to listen to the second two I was.”

There is a level of tolerance shown even in the parts that may have been distracting purely because of the efficacy of the music in providing a backdrop with which to relax. The reason that this section of the analysis was labelled passive listening was after reflection of condition three, where it will be made evident that my experience there was at times quite the opposite. From my own experiences with music and the way in which I engage with music, I found it interesting that in this context, despite often having an analytical listening style, while I was still engaging with the music on an emotional level, I wasn’t on a musicological level, which certainly helped for the experience to be more cohesive.

Aesthetic Appreciation aids protocol outcomes

Where this condition differed greatly from the first was in its ability to draw forth a strong emotional response, which was not something PMR was designed to produce. In isolation, especially a strong emotional response can detract from the protocol's aims. Despite this, the music enhanced the experience greatly when I wasn’t actively analysing it. The beauty found in the music produced a profound happiness response that was enabled by the protocol. Listening to the music in isolation is an enjoyable

experience for me, but I hadn't ever reacted to it in the same way as when it was listened to in conjunction with the protocol.

“Man this was my favourite session so far. The music was so beautiful and soothing, idk (I don't know) something about the last track in particular, by that point in the session you are so relaxed, and it just enhanced that feeling so much”.

This appreciation for the aesthetic beauty of the music alongside the protocol served as the most relaxing way I had, or would, experience PMR. Interesting to note here as well that, regarding biometric readings, it was this condition that exhibited my highest average heart rates on a per-session basis out of the whole study. So, while when looking at the graphs above it may appear that I was physically less relaxed, this can be interpreted as a positive emotional response that triggered elevated heart levels. While this stronger emotional response may not be what was intended for the protocol in isolation, adding a musical element that I am familiar with provides an alternative positive outcome for the intervention in that while relaxed I was also joyful and could appreciate the music itself in a new way.

Another factor that is traditionally seen as harmful to relaxation is when the music doesn't fall into certain musicological categories, such as those mentioned in the research context. This conditions music certainly does not fall exactly into those categories musically, and despite this, I still reported great relaxation coupled with enjoyment.

“Even though the last track had lyrics, the way they are mixed to pan around and seep in and out with the PMR protocol was quite beautiful.”

The concept of enhanced experience due to the pleasure of the musical stimuli run throughout this section of analysis. There was constant reference to this in response to questions of musical engagement and thoughts and emotions regarding the experience, where I had often responded positively to the stimuli. It was seen at the time as an immensely soothing, relaxing and enjoyable experience that was certainly enhanced by the presence of familiar music. In terms of describing how these feelings are to me personally, as an opera singer, I have been trained to perceive somatic shifts and so to experience them in a different setting is greatly appreciated. Relaxation in the context of this condition was felt to a far higher degree than relaxing my body to sing or to breathe properly before a phrase. It was a far deeper and more broad feeling of physical and emotional stillness that I have only experienced while in a state of flow as a singer, and even then, that is a far less present state than when actively focusing on the music and PMR in combination and being able to reflect so deeply upon the experience from a researcher's perspective.

Condition Three

The double-edged nature of musical engagement

Having now reflected upon the benefits from my positionality of passive listening and aesthetic appreciation of music in aiding in alternative protocol outcomes, condition three serves as a contrast in regard to these factors. This condition of curated music shows well how unfamiliar stimuli can detract from the protocol through active engagement and analysis of the music, which in turn distracts from properly being able to engage with PMR.

The first day exhibited multiple signs of distraction caused by the music and while the stimuli itself was by no means unpleasant, the nature of the tracks caused my mind to wander from the protocol. I was too intent on actively listening to the tracks from a musicological standpoint, and this analytical mindset had conflicting outcomes.

“The jazz and classical pieces chosen were I think too stimulating and I made a few minor timing errors in the protocol because I was too interested in the new stimuli that wasn’t familiar to me.”

A recurring subtheme that developed here was control. Throughout structured and non-structured journal entries across the first two days, I often make reference to the fact that I felt like having no say in the music was frustrating. There was a loss of agency as well as the knowledge at the time that I was getting too involved in the music, which compounded into a feeling of disappointment, having just experienced condition two, in which the results were so positive.

This combination of active musical engagement and loss of agency led to conflicting feelings after each session. I wasn’t as sure about whether or not the session was good, bad or neutral, and because of the stimuli I also was not as aware as to whether I had made any progress in developing a better muscle sense.

“By the end (of the session) though I felt similar (to before the session) despite the distractions so I’m not really sure how to interpret that, although even though the music was really nice I think I would still prefer direct control over it otherwise I risk becoming too physically and mentally involved in the music.”

There is far more ambiguity and confusion in post-session responses for the first two days of this condition than in contrast to the other conditions. Regarding physical state however, it can be said that the first session did still yield some positive outcomes, as while I wasn't able to specify why I was feeling better on a muscle grouping level, I did reflect that I felt marginally better overall. On day two however, there was only slight physical improvement and mentally I was less relaxed and more conflicted, which I noted was the first time I found a negative impact during the whole trial.

The second day was characterised by distraction and loss of agency, which was exacerbated by external factors such as work difficulties. Another sub-theme developed here was liminality and transition, or using the PMR sessions as a space between work and rest. With day two in particular, I came at the session with the mindset that the previous sessions had been a great way in which to relax after my workday, and so I had the preconceived notion that due to the efficacy of previous days, this would continue. However, due to the music being distracting through factors mentioned above, such as active listening, my experiences and stress during the day and a post-session feeling of lacking agency and unmet expectations, the session didn't go well.

“I was initially looking forward to the session today and then was slightly thrown off during due to the music somewhat clashing at times with the protocol. I have had similar days throughout this research trial that at the end of the day the protocol really helped to relax me and calm me however I think that wasn't entirely the experience I got today.”

While quite a long quote, it summarises well the double-edged nature of musical engagement from my frame of mind at the time. The combination of musical stimuli, the

mentioned subthemes of agency and the protocol being used in a way that fosters transition between work and relaxation, all combined to make the first two days a conflicting and thematically dissonant set of days.

Familiarity as a Gateway to Relaxation

Interestingly, the final day of this condition, as well as the whole trial, exhibited a marked shift in emotional and physical responses compared to the first two days. There was a level of apprehension shown towards the session, given the experience on day two, which shifted to a positive emotional and physical response to the end of the session. Familiarity served as the way in which the music could finally serve as an enhancement to the protocol as opposed to a distraction and my listening style shifted back to a far more passive experience.

Regarding external factors, I started from a much clearer headspace and was relaxed going into the session. There was a higher level of connection and awareness to the body, breath and emotions and a deep state of relaxation was achieved by the end.

“Today was the first time this set of music enhanced my engagement, I was relaxed going into the session and the music was familiar enough to me now that instead of critiquing it I could just enjoy it peacefully in the background.”

There was also a noted emotional response with constant reference to joy, relief and happiness, however as opposed to condition two, I believe now that this wasn't in response to the musical stimuli but rather the fact that I was able to have a more passive listening experience. This familiarity with the stimuli is an interesting concept from my positionality and how I analyse music as a listener. All music I listen to will be analysed,

but it is what I find in the music, whether that be complex melodic or rhythmic structure, interesting timbre, lyrics or tone that drives my love for that track. While outside of the context of PMR, I generally enjoy this active process if the curated music did not meet my expectations of these factors I don't think the experience would have been positive, even given familiarity as a factor. By day three, I had discerned an appreciation for the music through familiarity that let the experience become far more passive as a whole, coherent session.

“I could actually enjoy and appreciate the music today as it was familiar to me. I didn't automatically analyse it like I would with new music, and it wasn't distracting like yesterday when I don't think I was in the right frame of mind to enjoy it as well as it was still not familiar. I feel not only more calm than before the session but also happy at how the music felt right for me today.”

The takeaway from this condition then is that while familiarity with the stimuli helps greatly for me to be able to engage with the protocol in equal measure, the music has to also be a pleasant listening experience personally. I would hypothesise that given different tracks in a style that I was not only unfamiliar with but also aesthetically didn't appreciate, the outcomes would differ greatly. It is only through a combination of familiarity, aesthetic appreciation and passive listening that the protocol can still function as intended, enhanced by the music from my positionality.

Discussion

Having shown the results of both the reflexive thematic and descriptive statistical analysis, the following discussion will be split into two sections to address the research aims. The first will seek to synthesise and compare RTA with biometric data to assess with more accuracy the impact the music had on the PMR protocol and how it influenced my personal experience with the protocol. Secondly, to demonstrate how knowledge has been developed throughout the trial and research project, reflective considerations for future applications of music integration with progressive muscle relaxation will be made, as well as by examining the limitations of this project.

Biometric Comparison to Reflexive Thematic Analysis

To briefly summarise heart rate changes over the 9 days, it was found that:

- Heart rate across all variables decreased over the 9 days
- Condition One fell in the middle regarding heart rate averages
- Condition Two demonstrated the highest heart rate averages and variability
- Condition Three shows the lowest heart rate across all variables

When comparing these findings to those analysed through RTA, it is noted that there is both alignment and divergence from subjective experience. Misalignments between these two factors are valuable areas of inquiry in an autoethnographic context (Ellis, Adams and Bochner, 2010) and should help to provide meaningful discussion surrounding the topic area.

Condition One

Condition one was reflected upon as being effective in its ability to relax and relieve muscle tension. While biometrics from the first session don't entirely align with subjective experience of relaxation, this is to be expected as it was the first day of the trial. It is important to note regarding this point, and for the rest of the discussion, that emotional states do not always have immediate or consistent biological responses, given the research context under which application of PMR was carried out (Critchley and Harrison, 2013). As well as this, there is always risk of overvaluing quantification, which Lupton (2016) critiques as biometric reductionism. While biometric data can give insight into relaxation, it is limited in its ability to capture the complex nature of human emotion (Borgmann, 2000).

Day two showed far less pre-session nerves, a calmer demeanour, and task willingness, and proved to have the lowest averages across the condition. On day three, heart rate still decreased over time, but the averages remained higher than the previous session. From further analysis of the journal entries, there seemed to be some task resistance exhibited. Before the session that day, I was working on notes for the project and was slightly apprehensive to stop focusing on that task. As such, the session started slightly late, which may have impacted my mood. Smallwood and Schooler (2015) have examined how mental states fluctuate and affect our ability to engage with other tasks. In this context, it could be said that the mental inertia of working on the project before engaging with PMR may have influenced the session averages.

Despite this, HR did still decrease over time, showing that the protocol is still able to function to a degree, despite external factors or moods. This aligns with the research

done by Kim, (2008) who also found that PMR is robust in it's ability to carry out its aims in spite of external factors.

From the auto-ethnographer's perspective, another factor to consider when evaluating this increase in heart rate average on the third day, is that it was influenced by performance pressure. There may have been a level of subconscious want for alignment between biometric data and subjective data. While I am not stating this was the case for certain, this phenomenon has been observed by researchers such as St. Pierre (2007), and Sparkes (2020), who show how important it is to acknowledge that autoethnographic accounts can be performative in nature and shaped by the researcher having the role of participant as well.

Condition Two

The second condition shows higher average heart rates in every category when compared to the first condition, however interestingly also follows the same pattern as the last day of the condition, showing higher averages than the second to last. Once again, though, this is shown to be affected by external factors such as work stress and task hesitancy from journal analysis or a combination of both. What is of more import in regards to this condition, is the averages and minimums measured, which were higher than the first condition and that despite this, subjectively, the condition exhibited the strongest positive response. Heart rate did still decline throughout the sessions, but this reduction was not the most pronounced out of the conditions.

As opposed to Condition One, where each session was analysed individually, the following conditions will be observed more as a whole. It has already been shown that

there are day-to-day fluctuations in heart rate averages, and that PMR exists in a broader emotional and environmental context in relation to biometrics. This simply meaning that, as previously established, biometric indicators are not always an accurate indicator of internal emotional states (Critchley and Harrison, 2013).

This condition shows a strong emotional response not exhibited in the first condition, caused by the addition of musical stimuli, and notably stimuli with which I was familiar and had positive feelings towards. Researchers such as Pereira *et al.*, (2011) have shown that factors such as familiarity can greatly heighten emotional engagement. The increased HR averages are interesting because they challenge the assumption that lower heart rates mean increased relaxation, as subjectively, it was in this condition that I felt most relaxed, and align with studies that show emotional engagement increases heart rate (Rickard, 2004; Kreibig, 2010). The implication here is that PMR, for me, enabled the emotional response from the music by getting me to a point of relaxation that let me appreciate the music in a way I hadn't before. Instead of interpreting elevated HR as an indicator of stress, in this context, it reflects a deep emotional engagement and response to the musical stimuli. This interpretation shows the need and importance of contextualising biometric data in works that are autoethnographic in nature (Ellis, Adams and Bochner, 2010).

From a psychological perspective, Russell's (1980) dual-axis model of affect⁷ shows that valence and arousal do not necessarily need to be aligned to achieve relaxation. In this context, we can see that Condition One shows arousal due to relaxation, and Condition

⁷ This model proposes that emotional states can be understood along two dimensions: Valence (positive/negative emotion) and arousal (low to high physiological activation)

Two shows arousal due to emotional stimulation. Both conditions were effective overall in reducing stress and enhancing relaxation but adding a musical element to the protocol effects, at its core, the responses exhibited by the participant.

From my positionality as a musician, being able to experience familiar musical stimuli in an entirely new emotional light was profoundly meaningful upon reflection, one which I was quoted as saying:

“I had a really great time with this stimuli group, and I think it is something I can see myself incorporating into my everyday life just because of how calming it is.”

While Condition One was effective from a technical point of view, there is more value for me personally in the emotional resonance of Condition Two.

Condition Three

Having now discussed how Condition Two was an experience shaped and defined by the emotionally stimulating application of familiar music, Condition Three can serve as a contrasting lens with much to be extrapolated from the dissonance between biometrics and RTA.

In the same way that Condition Two shows how important it is to contextualise biometric data with subjective experience (Ellis, Adams and Bochner, 2010), it is shown that while HR measures across all metrics and conditions were lowest in Condition Three, journal entries reflect a more complex and ambivalent response for the first two days. Rather than clear disengagement, these sessions were characterised by reflective uncertainty regarding the musical stimuli. This was made evident on the second day, when the musical choices were perceived to clash with the protocol. Despite the greatly lowered

averages, this condition shows the first stagnation in heart rate decrease during the second day session, which was the first day in which HR did not trend downward by the end of the session. The only day in which the experience aligned with biometric data was day three.

To start, this condition represents the first significant emotional shift, from uncertainty to positivity, which suggests that familiarity with the stimuli as well as comfortability are both important factors at play (Kabat-Zinn, 2003; Tang, Hölzel and Posner, 2015). Heart rate across the first session indicates a moderate level of biometric relaxation which was echoed in journal comments that emphasise that physically, I felt more relaxed post-session. Where biometrics are unable to add nuance however was in the initial distraction felt by the new stimuli as well as the conflicting thoughts I was exhibiting regarding how music fit into the protocol. Gabrielsson, (2001) shows that this response is not uncommon however. Drawing on research done with over a 1000 participants, it was found that delayed and evolving reactions towards new stimuli are commonplace. Context also does matter; while the journal entries clearly show that I found the music enjoyable, this may have simply been the wrong context in which to enjoy it in, as it was detracting from the protocol at times. Music has been found to elicit different emotional responses in different contexts (Lundqvist *et al.*, 2009) which was certainly the case here. Heart rate average decreased on day two however, over the session remained consistent instead of trending downwards as it did in previous sessions. This was most likely due to a combination of factors, such as loss of agency and the protocol not meeting the mental expectation I had that, as with the previous sessions, I would leave feeling better. The mindset of the subject and their expectations can play a crucial role in therapeutic

outcomes (Benedetti, 2009). However, by this point at day 8 it appears that the routine of constant engagement with the protocol was yielding good physical results and as a compounding effect, still reduced HR despite the negative subjective experience.

The fact that there was still a strong indication of physical relaxation in the biometric data aligns with Kabat-Zinn's, (2003) research which shows how time and repetition in relation to mindfulness-based practices yield more meaningful and consistent benefits. In relation to decreased heart rate, there is also the perspective that repetition is not always beneficial and that without emotional engagement, habituation and disengagement occur, which lead to decreased arousal and in turn HR (Farb *et al.*, 2007). In this context, that may be challenged however by reflective entries that demonstrate a post-session emotional response, or in the case of day one a curiosity response, albeit tinged with conflict.

But a strong conclusion to draw from the biometrics is challenging the assumption that reduced HR directly correlates to a better relaxation response (Thayer *et al.*, 2012), which as demonstrated here, aligns with findings from Critchley and Harrison (2013), who demonstrate the complexity of physiological data's correlation to lived experience.

The shift to emotional positivity on day three was interesting from the perspective that, unlike Condition Two, the musical stimuli in Condition Three did not increase HR. Overall metrics from this final day were, in fact, quite the opposite, showing lower averages across all observed factors. There may be something to be said then for curated music's ability, in my case, to elicit a more traditional response that aligns with the aims of the PMR protocol. The removal of choice, emotional familiarity and control over the stimuli from Condition Two was replaced, by the final day, with familiar but emotionally detached

musical stimuli. The impact here then that music had was not to elicit a strong emotional response but to passively aid the protocol, and so this condition shows a lack of arousal but a return to positive valence in which the pleasant relaxation of the protocol was at the forefront of the experience and not the external stimuli.

Both Conditions Two and Three shift from active to passive listening, but this is made far more evident in Condition Three due to the subjective experience analysed. The way in which each individual experiences a given musical stimuli will always differ (Schäfer *et al.*, 2013) but from my positionality, a passive experience that enhances the protocol, while occasionally eliciting a strong positive emotional response, is observed to be the ideal experience.

Reflective Considerations and Future Applications

In addressing the research aims, it is important to demonstrate how knowledge surrounding the topic area has been developed. The following section will examine what this autoethnographic exploration has revealed regarding curated, non-choice and non-musical environments in the context of PMR. Furthermore, by reflective consideration of the limitations of this study, while no generalisations can be made, there may be room to make suggestions towards research design and methodological refinement for future research.

Conditions Two and Three have revealed how the interplay between biometric data and subjective experience complicate simplistic interpretations of relaxation outcomes. It has been shown that in the context of this study, musical engagement and its ties to PMR outcomes can vary greatly based on factors such as familiarity, agency and emotional

attachment to the stimuli. While HR reductions were measured, because of the aforementioned factors, thematic analysis reveals the necessity of a mixed methods approach by providing an interpretative lens (Braun and Clarke, 2006) with which to view the data. Condition One provides a strong baseline for comparison through its traditional outcomes and emphasises how across the other conditions, while biometric relaxation was sometimes achieved in subjectively conflicted sessions, qualitative reflections show in detail the dissonance between factors such as expectation, agency, valence and arousal.

These reflections were only made possible through autoethnography. Where I am situated as the researcher and participant has allowed for a unique experience, allowing deep insight into an individual's positionality and integration of lived experience (Ellis, Adams and Bochner, 2010). Having said that, though a unique and potentially unrepeatable experience precludes generalisability and introduces epistemological⁸ limitations. While this research has shown that providing choice and actualisation is a powerful tool for enabling positive outcomes for myself, this has limited practical application for others. The individual nature of musical appreciation and perception is shaped by personal history, mood, enculturation and so on (DeNora, 2000) make broadly applicable conclusions in regards to this research impossible.

This study does however, provide an alternative view to that of the work done by Lundqvist *et al.*, (2009) and Koelsch, (2020) in that it poses the question of whether music should help to enhance PMR through emotional engagement or support it in its initial aims. As a

⁸ The theory of knowledge, its validity, methods, scope and distinction between justified belief and opinion

combined intervention, it seems as though the outcomes of both music therapy and PMR should be taken into consideration as opposed to one or the other. Further inquiry into curated “emotionally neutral” music could serve as a way in which to examine if PMR could function as a consistent aid for participants with heightened emotional sensitivity or neurodivergent traits. Contrasting with whether they would benefit more from providing a PMR practitioner with their choice of music, through which the practitioner could choose a selection that aligns most with traditional musicological factors for relaxation (Gaston, 1951; Hanser, 1985), could provide a rich insight into these two alternative methods music music-assisted PMR.

Given the lack of research, established in the research context, surrounding the effects of specific musical stimuli on participant engagement with PMR, the natural recommendation for future research is a larger sample size. The connotations surrounding how music can be used to elicit new and stronger emotional responses in conjunction with PMR may also be in need of further evaluation to make professional recommendations. HR data in this context is difficult to consistently interpret, as it is not a clinical environment which constrains interpretation (Berntson *et al.*, 1997). Where this is valuable is providing a comfortable and familiar environment in which relaxation may be obtained more consistently. However, stronger methodological practice in incorporating more robust multimodal biometrics (EEG, ECG, HRV) could provide further enhanced value when combined with qualitative diaries to capture both physiological and phenomenological aspects of PMR as a mixed intervention with music therapy.

Ultimately, this study shows the need for more participant-centred interpretivist research focused on PMR protocols that account for the fluidity of musical responses. Examining

differing levels of control over musical stimuli throughout different demographics, backgrounds, and longer-term engagement may yield protocols that are better suited to individual needs, in turn enhancing PMR's accessibility and effectiveness.

Conclusion

This study set out to explore the impact of different musical stimuli on my experience with a PMR protocol. The aim was not to be able to draw definitive conclusions regarding efficacy but broaden understanding through a mixed-methods research design situated in autoethnographic inquiry.

It was made evident from an autoethnographic perspective that music greatly impacted my experience, thoughts and feelings regarding engagement with Progressive Muscle Relaxation. It did this through a variety of factors, such as enhancing emotional responses towards musical stimuli, which served to provide PMR with an alternative therapeutic outcome, showing that choice and self-actualisation can be driving factors in one's ability to engage with the protocol from a musical perspective and that relaxation is not a linear or straightforward response when combined with unfamiliar stimuli.

Through analysis of mixed-methods data, knowledge was developed in relation to not only the protocol but the nuanced way in which music plays a role in emotional and somatic factors and shows clearly that interpretation of quantitative data through a reflexive thematic lens is essential in providing context for said data.

While this study focused on the experience of one individual, it ultimately raises broader questions regarding the alternative outcomes demonstrated by music-assisted PMR,

ways in which it can be developed to suit different needs and personalities and how providing musical choice to the participant can directly shape their experience.

Appendix

1. Houston Centre for Valued Living PMR protocol - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=lclQSzurKUI>
2. Reflexive Journal –

Structured Journaling Prompts – Daily Post-PMR Session

1. Session Context

What time did you complete today's PMR session?

What was the setting/environment like (e.g., lighting, temperature, interruptions)?

Which music condition was used today? (No music Self-selected music Supervisor-selected music)

Which session out of the 3-day split did you complete today? (Day 1 Day 2 Day 3)

2. Physical Sensations

How would you describe your physical state before the session? (e.g., tension, restlessness, fatigue)

How would you describe your physical state after the session?

Were there any body areas that were difficult to relax? If so, which ones?

Did you notice any bodily changes (e.g., breath, heartbeat, posture)?

3. Emotional and Psychological State

What emotions or thoughts were most present before the session?

How did those shift (if at all) during and after the session?

Did you experience any moments of mental clarity or distraction?

4. Response to Music (if applicable)

How did the music affect your engagement with the PMR technique?

Did you find the music soothing, distracting, evocative, or neutral?

Did any imagery, memories, or associations arise in response to the music?

Why/how was the music chosen for this session?

(If no music was used, reflect on the silence: Did it feel spacious, uncomfortable, grounding, etc.?)

5. Sense of Connection

How connected to your body, breath, and emotions did you feel during today's session?

How would you describe your sense of presence or awareness?

Appendix

6. Overall Impact

How would you rate today's session in terms of its overall effectiveness? (1 = not effective at all, 5 = extremely effective): 1 2 3 4 5

What, if anything, would you change about the session next time?

Is there anything you're curious to explore further?

7. Further thoughts

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